

NUTRI•KNOW

STRUVITE (IT)

RENURE (BE)

GAS LOOP (IT)

POCKETBOER 2 (BE)

SOS_AQUAE (IT)

Grass2Algae (BE)

FERTICOOP-GO (ES)

MOPS (IE)

Manure Management Tool (ES)

Duncannon Blue Flag Farming (IE)

Manure Concentrator (ES)

Biorefinery Glas (IE)

Exchanging easy-to-understand nutrient management knowledge with farmers

NUTRI-KNOW aims to improve nutrient management practices in agriculture by establishing an ongoing cycle of knowledge exchange for the benefit of both farmers and the environment.

RENURE

Manure-derived ammonium salts recovered via stripping and scrubbing process

Why consider this innovation?

If you're running a large livestock farm, you're likely producing more manure than your land can legally handle. That excess nitrogen is not just a regulatory headache—it's costing you money to transport or process. The stripper-scrubber **removes the nitrogen** from slurry and turns it into a **usable fertiliser (ammonium sulfate or nitrate)**.

That means:

- **Less nitrogen left in the slurry** → easier to spread or dispose of
- **More nitrogen in the recovered product** → reusable or even sellable
- **Lower transport costs** → no need to move so much slurry around.

What is the investment?

CAPEX	€200,000 – €500,000 (for mid- to large-scale stripper-scrubber systems)
Operational Cost (OPEX)	€9 – €14 per ton of thin fraction treated

Key parameters impacting Return on Investment (ROI)

- Manure type (pig > cattle in NH_4^+ content)
- Scale (>20,000 tons/year needed for viability)
- Availability of residual heat (e.g., from digesters)
- Existing N removal technologies (for synergy)

When does it start paying off?

The system starts to make economic sense at **large pig farms processing at least 20,000 tons of manure a year**. It can save you up to **€1.80 per ton of manure treated**, especially if you're in a region with strict manure rules or high "manure pressure" (meaning it's expensive or hard to spread excess nitrogen).

You also create ammonium salts that can replace bought-in nitrogen, reducing your fertiliser bill. And if future EU rules fully allow **RENURE** products, these salts could become even more valuable.

Stripping-scrubbing unit at INAGRO (Flanders, BE)

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